

The hypermobility of rock avalanches, a review

Andrea M. Deganutti PhD

CNR - National Researches Council of Italy - Institute of Polar Sciences

andreamaria.deganutti@cnr.it

Abstract

Rock avalanches are very large and very fast landslides characterised by volumes above two million cubic metres, with velocities of the order of tens of meter per second and as a consequence, are among the most powerful and dangerous natural phenomena.

These landslides show a particular behaviour: when their volume exceeds 10^7 m^3 the fragmented rock mass travels longer than one would expect by the normal Coulomb friction mechanics, which otherwise works rather well for rockslides of smaller volumes; this behaviour can be called “the hypermobility of rock avalanches”.

This strange behaviour sparked a number of studies on its possible cause (or causes) among solid Earth scholars, but none of the related theories advanced so far has been widely accepted by the scientific community.

In this article a literature review is given on the most important scientific works on this yet unsolved problem.

1. General description of rock avalanches features

The unusually long runout of very large rock slides, called also “Sturzstrom” by the pioneer rock avalanche scholar Albert Heim, who was the first to observe and describe in details a rock avalanche (1882, quoted by Hsü, 1978): referring to the Elm event (Switzerland, Glarus, 11 September 1881) which is still a not completely understood physical phenomenon.

Since Heim, many earth scientists have approached the behaviour of rock avalanches from different points of view, in terms of descriptions of real cases, statistical analyses of data in the literature, and proposing physical explanations of the strange behaviour of sturzstroms.

Heim described the Elm rock avalanche deposit as similar to glaciers and, from eyewitness descriptions of the rock debris motion, stated that the rockfall, after a first phase in which it behaved as a rigid body, disintegrated into debris and then flowed. So he introduced his basic interpretation of a sturzstrom motion: “rockfalls do not slide, they crash, and their debris flows”.

This statement is supported, among others, by Hsu (1978), Kilburn (2001) etc., and gave origin to the long debated question of “flow vs. slide” in the interpretation of the motion of rock avalanches.

In his works Heim (1882, 1932) used the German term sturzstrom (literally: fall stream) to refer to the last phase of the slide in which the rock debris mass moved along the main

of the flowing mass, representing at every point the kinetic energy of the flow (or the losses of the potential energy).

With reference to Figure 1, and following the Coulomb law of friction, we have for the apparent friction coefficient:

$$f = \tan \alpha = H L^{-1} \tag{1}$$

where H is the total vertical drop of the rock slide and L is the horizontal projection of the travel distance. Most scholars consider the *fahrböschung* as α .

A normal value for this coefficient is considered about 0.6, or 0.62 ($\tan 32^\circ$) (Hsü 1975) with reference to normal repose angle for granular materials and, by comparison between this latter value with that from a real case of *sturzstrom*, a measure of its hypermobility can be inferred. Hsu introduced in this way the *excessive travel distance*:

$$L_e = L - H [\tan(32^\circ)]^{-1} \tag{2}$$

Where L_e is the excessive travel distance, L and H as in eq. 1.

The physical meaning of L_e is the travel of the debris mass beyond the distance one can expect from a landslide which travels with a normal coefficient of friction. Hsu stated that this parameter is a more correct measure of the hypermobility of rock avalanches than the *fahrböschung* since the latter has no precise physical meaning and is at least inaccurate to characterize the low friction effect.

The excessive travel distance has then been used by some authors; for instance, Nicoletti and Sorriso Valvo (1991) proposed the dimensionless ratio L_e/L as a mobility index.

Figure 2 Logarithmic graph of apparent friction (H/L) vs. Slide volume. Data from 315 cases and are aggregated into four different categories. R is the coefficient of correlation. Data after Pollet (2004).

Many authors have used data from a number of *sturzstrom* events to highlight *sturzstrom* hypermobility, generally drawing a logarithmic graph (Figure 2) of $H L^{-1}$ vs. Volume. The

data are generally scattered in the graph, depending on which events have been considered and on their number, but it is nevertheless obvious to observe the effect of decreasing apparent friction ($H L^{-1}$) with increasing volume.

Hsü (1975) and Hungr (1990) commented that data scattering stating that it seems more correct to speak of a different behaviour of slides when their volume is above a few millions of m^3 , rather than a systematic increase of mobility with volume; Davies and McSaveney (1999) confirmed this, showing that behaviour of large volume events is self-consistent and different from those of smaller ones.

Figure 3 Displacement of the centre of mass of some rock avalanches. Data after Legros (2001).

Legros (2001) showed that the size effect is manifest also considering the displacement of the centre of mass of the fallen debris mass (Figure 3).

The first to formalize the Heim observations about sturzstroms was Scheidegger (1973) who, assuming that "the rapid motion of a small mass down a scree slope is governed by the laws of dry friction" found that rock debris avalanches travel to a maximum distance that is consistent with normal values of internal and basal friction (considering the angle of repose of rock debris: $\alpha=30^\circ \div 40^\circ$ which corresponds to a friction coefficient of $0.57 \div 0.83$) up to a volume around $10^5 m^3$ and that their behaviour changes above that value of volume becoming the maximum runout significantly higher than that the larger the volume.

He did not propose a possible mechanism to explain this behaviour but, considering the data from 33 rock avalanches, calculated a regression curve between the logarithm of the friction coefficient (calculated as HL^{-1}) and the slide volume, in order to provide a tool for the prediction of maximum runout for potentially dangerous rock slopes:

$$\log(H L^{-1})=a*\log Vol + b \quad (3)$$

It is interesting to note that he stated that there seems to be no direct correlation between the volume and the velocity of rock avalanche, postulating otherwise a direct correlation between friction and volume; it has however to be noted that this observation is based only on 6 values (out of 33 cases) of landslide velocity, values indirectly calculated ex post facto.

Following the Scheidegger work, several other scholars, using different and more or less rich landslide data bases, proposed statistical relation for the prediction of sturzstroms runout (Hsu 1975, Li 1983, Voight et al. 1985, Nicoletti and Sorriso-Valvo 1991, Legros 2001, etc.), a general comparison among their proposed relations is given in Pollet (2004). All of them proposed an equation of a statistical regression between the apparent friction coefficient (HL^{-1}) and the landslide volume formally identical to the Scheidegger one.

The coefficients **a** and **b** of the equation 3 proposed by these authors differ for they used data from different groups of slides (the number of considered events varies from 15 to 71), introducing also volcanic slides (Voight and al. 1985, Hayashi and Self, 1992) submarine and extraterrestrial slides (Legros 2001).

A table with the resultant values for **a** and **b** (equation 3) is given by Pollet (2004) for the most prominent studies; it is possible to see that the correlation coefficient of those regressions are not very good since the scatter of data is generally wide in all the databases used and, reflecting the fact that the data come from different group of events, the values of **a** and **b** vary broadly.

A special case seems constituted by Martian slides for which McEwen (1989) found a regression with a correlation of 0.90; but Legros (2001) found 0.73 with the same data. Thus the applicability of these equations for the assessment of the possible maximum runout of a potential rock avalanche is limited; moreover one has to add the uncertainty linked to the estimation of the possible slide volume.

To avoid this latter difficulty Nicoletti and Sorriso-Valvo (1991) propose a simple equation according to which the runout distance of large surzstroms (with volume between $5 \cdot 10^6$ and $1.6 \cdot 10^9$) ranges from 3.2 to 8 times the slide height, depending on their classification of low, moderate and high energy dissipative landslides; the same authors anyway underline that this simple relation is to be considered a rough one, valid only as a first approach.

Davies (1982) working on a sample of 14 slides with volumes ranging from 10^7 to 10^{12} m^3 , argued that the shape of rock avalanches deposits do not depend on the fall height, which only causes data to scatter, and obtained a regression between volume and deposit length with a correlation coefficient as high as 0.92; it is interesting to note that this is much higher than those obtained for regressions between the fahrböschung (or $H L^{-1}$) and the total travelled distance; on the other hand one could also observe that it is rather obvious that a debris mass of a larger volume will occupy a larger deposition area (and so a longer deposit). Moreover he ascribed the residual scatter of data to the deposit shapes which depend on the morphology of the receiving valley and stated that, with more and more precise data available, a family of trend lines for deposits of different shapes could be inferred.

Davies' conclusions follow the Hsu and Heim statement that the sturzstroms in the flowing stage have no "memory" of the first phase of the slide and of the fall height.

Pollet (2004) provided the most complete database about rock avalanches, gathering data from literature about 316 slides including gigantic slides on Moon and Mars and terrestrial submarine ones, with volumes ranging from $6 \cdot 10^3$ to $17.9 \cdot 10^9$ m³. In the relative graph $H L^{-1}$ vs. Volume (Figure 2).

Other interesting observations from the wide literature on this question emerge: McEwen (1989) stated that the slope of $H L^{-1}$ vs V correlation line for Martian rock avalanches is nearly identical to that of terrestrial slides (using Scheidegger's rock avalanches data for the latter) concluding that the effect of low friction is present in a lower gravity environment as well (gravitational acceleration on Mars is 3.72 ms^{-2}). However he observed that there is an offset between the two trend lines: at a given value of $H L^{-1}$, the Martian rock avalanches are on average about 50 to 100 times larger in volume than terrestrial ones (Figure 2.2).

He explained the offset stating the effect of a high yield strength of the flowing debris mass; with reference to a Bingham rheology, the slide will have a thicker deposit with a lower gravity. Moreover he said that this is a general characteristic of sturzstroms and that a size effect mechanism for rock avalanches has to be consistent with the presence of high yield strength in the flowing debris mass.

Davies and McSaveney (1999) explained the offset by the larger relief available on Mars than on Earth.

2. Proposed Mechanisms for rock avalanches long runout

Of course almost all of the scientists who have been puzzled by the rock avalanches low friction behaviour, tried to find out the physical process that produces such a behaviour. Moreover many among them proposed some mechanism able to explain also other generally observed rock avalanche features, above all the retention in the deposit of the original sequential order of rock layers before the fall and the presence of ridges in the distal part of deposits, suggesting a sudden stop of the debris mass in those regions.

- Fluidization

With this term various authors meant a reduction of friction in a granular flowing mass such that it would behave similarly to a fluid. This process, occurring in the whole debris mass, would be able to explain the long runout of rock avalanches; it could however have a similar effect if it occurred only in particular regions, especially near the underlying bedrock surface. Different causes and mechanisms have been proposed for fluidization.

- Heim (1882, 1932), stated that the Elm event was characterized by three distinct phases: the fall, the jump and the surge. He described the last as a flow of dry rock debris particles (sturzstrom). He observed also that the stratigraphic sequence of the rock before the fall

was essentially preserved in the final configuration of the deposit, a characteristic since observed in many other rock avalanche deposits. Heim stated that the flow motion of the rock mass (once it had been disintegrated by the fall) was caused by the continuous impacts among the rock particles and this process could not be considered similar to a viscous flow of a fluid. He postulated that this peculiar process was dominant in all the large rock slides which showed a low friction, long travel character.

Hsu (1975) embraced Heim's theory and observed that he postulated a grain motion that would be described by Bagnold (1954, 1956) some twenty years later in his works on turbulent flow of a dispersion of cohesionless grains.

Later, Hsu (1978) deepened his position suggesting the presence of rock dust as an interstitial fluid in the grain dispersive flow, approaching in this way the Bagnold (1954, 1956) theory: the rock dust would keep the granules in suspension reducing the energy dissipation due to friction.

- Davies (1982) proposed mechanical fluidization as a mechanism similar to that introduced by Heim and Hsu, stating (quoting Bagnold experiments as well) a dilation of the grain mass due to high impulsive contact pressure and the consequent reduction of internal friction. This mechanism is produced by high energy and high shear rate, concentrated in the region near the contact of the sliding mass with the stationary underlying rock bed. In this way the upper part of the rock mass remains essentially unsheared with the consequence of preservation of the retention of sequential order. The reduction of the mass velocity under a critical value should abruptly diminish the degree of dilation in the shearing layer leading to a sudden stop of the front of the landslide; the following part of the slide will be forced to stop by the already still distal part giving origin to the lateral and transversal ridges often present in the most advanced part of sturzstroms deposits. Mechanical fluidization has been adopted (sometimes with some variation) by a few other authors to explain several cases of real rock avalanches (Körner 1977, Voight 1978, Mc Saveney 1975). Schneider and Fisher (1998) studying an ancient volcano in Central France, stated the applicability of this mechanism to large volcanic debris avalanche. Hungr (1990), however, questioned this mechanism stating the lack of theoretical demonstration and that there is no field evidence nor laboratory definitive proof of such a behaviour.

- McSaveney (1975), in his very detailed study on the Sherman Glacier rock avalanche, suggested the existence of mechanical fluidization due to ground vibrations from the earthquake that triggered the slide; he suggested a kind of hybrid motion mechanism for the $10.1 \cdot 10^6 \text{ m}^3$ debris mass: a sliding motion on the snow covered glacier surface with a friction as low as 0.1, above which the fluidized rock fragmented particles were in laminar motion; he noted the presence of a "crust" of undeforming material on the slide surface; this "carapace" would come from the Bingham rheology (presence of a shear strength) he adopted for the flowing mass to explain the deposition features of that sturzstrom, in particular the presence of large amount of weathered mountain surface on the surface of the rock avalanche deposit (Kent 1966). In addition to grain dispersive impact flow (with or without rock dust), fluidization can be the result of different (at least partially) mechanical causes: trapped air, pressurized water vapour, and acoustic vibrations.

- Air cushion theory

Shreve (1959, 1968a, 1968b) proposed a compressed air cushion as a frictionless layer at the bottom of the slide, above this cushion the slide would ride like a hovercraft (Davies 1982). Studying the Blackhawk slide in California (and later the Sherman Glacier rock avalanche in Alaska) he stated that a large amount of air was trapped beneath the rock mass as it "jumped" at high velocity over a morphological step, then compressed to generate a very low friction lubrication layer on which the rock sheet easily slid on the lower gentle slope. He asserted that this peculiar kind of motion explains all of the principal physical features of the slide deposition lobe, in particular the preservation of the original sequential order of the rock formations. For a while this theory was considered very promising, even if some doubts were raised about the possibility that the air cushion theory could well explain the Blackhawk slide deposit features (Johnson 1978).

Fluidization by trapped air (Kent 1966): an upward flow of compressed air, trapped by the rock mass during the initial stage of the fall, keep the debris in a dilated state, so the friction among the rock clasts is reduced and this permits the slide to travel for long distances. For the two authors the mechanism is able to explain the fluidization of the mass and is supported by deposit morphology and by field evidence and witnesses experience of high pressure air blast associated to recent rock avalanche events (Frank and Madison Canyon slides).

This theory has been widely questioned (Hungar 1981, Hungar and Morgenstern 1984) since the body of a rock avalanche is far from a condition of airtight compactness and the compressed air, if present, would escape quickly through the moving debris mass; moreover there is lack of physical evidence for fluidization (Cruden and Hungar 1986) in real cases and in laboratory experiments.

Air cushion mechanism and the trapped air fluidization (Kent 1966) were almost abandoned when sturzstrom-like deposits were recognised on the airless surface of the Moon (Guest, 1971; Howard, 1973) even if Legros (2001) argued that terrestrial-like rock avalanches are extremely rare on the Moon and some of them are associated with impact craters and so the avalanche material could have been transported as impact ejecta as well.

A variation of this theory foresees the presence of water vapour generated by the presence of pore water and by the heat due to friction (Habib 1975, Pautre et al. 1974) along the sliding surface; Habib demonstrated that in presence of high pressure from the rock body and a sliding speed higher than a critical value, the possible pore water vaporizes. As in the case of air basal lubrication this mechanism requires a compact rock mass to prevent water vapour to escape, and moreover it implies the assumption of a very high thickness of the shearing block to ensure the high pressure necessary for water vaporization. Finally, there is no record of any substantiating field evidence.

- Self-lubrication

Erismann (1979, 1986) introduced the concept of self-lubrication as the most promising explanation of the size effect showed by rock avalanches. His idea starts from some evidence of rock melts (frictionites) on the sliding surface of the pre-historical Koefels landslide (Oetztal, Austria) and observed that the heat generated on the sliding plane is proportional to the mass thickness and so it looks reasonable as a size effect physical cause; moreover the bad heat conductivity of rock should ease the melting process. For calcareous rock avalanches Erismann (stating the Flims giant landslide as an example) proposed the high temperature tribological dissociation of rock as a possible mechanism.

The latter process falls into the gas lubrication group since the dissociation of CaCO_3 produces gaseous CO_2 ($\text{CaCO}_3 \rightarrow \text{CaO} + \text{CO}_2$). The difficulties in this case are the same of water vapour generation and basal air lubrication, i.e. gas proof sliding mass, lateral constraints, lack of field evidence (Hungar 1990). So the Erisman self-lubrication theory would work only for siliceous rock.

- Other proposed mechanisms

Other authors proposed different mechanisms, often, but not only, constituted by a hybrid combination of two or more previously presented mechanisms.

- Nicoletti and Sorriso Valvo (1991) studying a sample of 40 rock avalanches, proposed "geomorphic controls" as the main explanation for rock avalanches mobility. They considered three general categories of geomorphic controls: channelling by lateral constraints, free lateral and downward spreading, and frontal impacting (as on the opposite slope of a valley). Consequently they called the first type of control as "low energy dissipative", the second and the third as "moderate" and "high" energy dissipative controls. Following this scheme, the mobility of sturzstroms decreases from the first to the last type.

- Evans (1995) studying the rock avalanches in the Canadian Cordillera, and noticing that most of them shows enhanced mobility, stated the possible presence of different mechanisms acting separately or together as well.

For the landslides which did not flow/slide on glaciated terrain (e.g. the famous Sherman slide), he proposed the fluidization of valley fill under undrained loading conditions as the most probable low friction mechanism. Otherwise he said that for debris avalanche on glaciers, low basal friction sliding is realistic and the mobility can in this case be enhanced by the melting of ice and snow due to load pressure and frictional heating.

He admitted also the possibility that lateral moraines can channelize the debris mass and so reducing the energy loss (as proposed by Nicoletti and Sorriso Valvo, 1991).

- Watson and Wright (1967) with reference to an old (about 10.000 years) event, the gigantic (volume of 30 km^3) Saidmarreh landslide in Iran, rejected as improbable and with

lack of field evidences the air cushion mechanism and also water lubrication, previously proposed by Harrison and Falcon (1938) for the Saidmarreh landslide. Instead they stated a low friction sliding on the gypsum bedrock of the valley, further eased by pulverized marl.

- Erismann (1986) defending his proposal for self-lubrication by rock melting, described as possible low friction mechanisms for landslides also rolling (presence of clasts able to rotate at the base of the sliding mass, so acting as roll bearings) and bouncing of the mass on the sliding surface irregularities. He stated the energy economy of these mechanisms that can act together, but concluded that they can have a role only for small volumes of rock since large ones would induce immediate crushing of the "rollers" and bouncing can have a role only occasionally and for some event (e.g. the Huascarán slide).

- Campbell and his co-authors (1995) with a study on computer simulation of rock avalanches by means of a large number of circular particles stated that the apparent friction coefficient is an increasing function of shear rate and that larger slides travel with higher thickness and so with lower shear rate; combining these two statements they explained the size effect of sturzstrom, even if they admitted that no current granular flow theory predicts such behaviour. So, at last, they invoked an unknown rheological behaviour following which rock avalanches travel in a transitional regime between rapid and quasi-static flow motion. At the end this hypothesis seems rather weak.

- Another transport mechanism is described by Pollet and Schneider (2004) who, studying the giant prehistoric Flims sturzstrom deposit, observed a particular texture of the material in the proximal and median axis regions. The fabric is a well recognizable structure of surfaces following the original sedimentary bedding of limestone and, according to authors, this structure suggests a slab on slab transport mechanism with finely fragmented fault-like gouge between sliding surfaces, this gouge formation assures high dilatancy and a consequent reduction of friction. The authors admitted that this particular transport mechanism is difficult to be generalized, volcanic sturzstroms, for instance, usually do not show a stratified structure.

- A more recent proposal

Davies and McSaveney (1999, 2002, 2006), Davies et al (2007) studying rock avalanches deposits in New Zealand, observed that the material is pervasively fragmented with smaller clasts in the lower part of deposits, often immersed in a matrix constituted of finely comminuted rock granules. Even apparently intact boulders and outcrops in deposits at a close inspection result highly fragmented (Campbell et al. 1995, Schneider and Fisher 1998, Watson and Wright, 1967, etc.), Shreve (1959, 1968a) called "3D jigsaw puzzle effect" this configuration of not much deformed shattered rock.

The observation of various degree of fragmentation is almost ubiquitous in field descriptions of rock avalanche deposits and, even if some of scholars (Genevois, 2007) think that the fragmentation process is mostly concentrated in the first stage of the fall, all of them acknowledge that fragmentation is a fundamental process in sturzstroms.

Starting from the consideration that none of the previously proposed rock avalanche hypermobility mechanisms is completely satisfying, Davies and McSaveney studied the effect on sturzstroms mobility of dynamic fragmentation, given its general importance in the process.

Schneider et al. (1999) studying the deposit features of the ancient Flims (Switzerland) giant rock avalanche, stressed the important role of rock comminution in the emplacement mechanism, in particular they emphasized the dilatancy effect produced by dynamic fragmentation with a resulting reduction in apparent friction.

Pollet and Schneider (2004) in the already described slab-on-slab mechanism proposal for the runout of the same rock avalanche, again gave to fragmentation an important role, but they, introducing the dispersive inflation concept, used fragmentation as a precursory step in the complex slab-on-slab transport mechanism. They acknowledged that this model is applicable only to sub horizontal stratified rock (Pollet et al., 2005).

Otherwise Davies and McSaveney stated that dynamic fragmentation is a necessary and sufficient condition for long runout, even if they admitted that it is not the only process contributing to runout being granular flow another necessary condition. So, dynamic fragmentation would have a prominent role in sturzstroms long runout and also in other geologic phenomena like long- runout, low angle block slides and fault ruptures, phenomena that require low friction to explain observations.

The dynamic fragmentation basic mechanism is described by Davies and McSaveney as follows: under the motion conditions relative to one of those low friction phenomena, the flowing grains of rock tend to form grain bridges (or arches) which are chains of particles aligned in the direction of the maximum compressive stress of the flowing mass (45° to the motion direction). The compressive stress is transmitted through the contact between grains during motion, until the failing of the bridge. The formation of grain bridges in granular flow is a well recognized characteristic of this type of motion (Sammis and Stacey, 1994; Liu et al., 1995; Neddermann, 1992). A bridge can fail for buckling (slip or rotation of any grain) or when the weakest grain in the bridge is stressed over its strength (Sammis et al., 1987). In this case, prior to failing, a grain of intact unjointed rock is stressed and the consequent deformation imply a storage of elastic energy in the particle until, when the rock strength is exceeded, it breaks releasing the stored energy about half of which (Grady and Kipp, 1987) is converted to kinetic energy of the resulting fragments.

This emission of energy can be explosive (Bieniawski, 1968). The effect on the surroundings is an isotropic dispersive stress and the resultant of the fragment momenta with respect to the original centre of mass is null. In static (or quasi-static) condition a stressed rock sample begins to break when its unconfined compressive strength (UCS) is reached, but in presence of dynamic conditions, a rapidly loaded rock fails when its Hugoniot elastic limit (HEL) is exceeded. The HEL is normally higher than the UCS and for a brittle rock it is around the order of 1 GPa (Melosh, 1997), so the released energy can be around a value of this order. Davies and McSaveney (2006) stressed that the dynamic fragmentation is different than collapse, being the latter a process of rupture of a piece of

rock along pre-existing joints with no energy release, given the low strength of a joint. In the case of rock avalanches most of the fragmentation process that takes place just after the initial collapse of the rock mass is of this type, while dynamic fragmentation mostly characterizes the following runout motion.

During the runout the process of dynamic fragmentation generates an internal dispersive stress in the longitudinal direction that makes the debris mass spread to a greater extent than would occur without fragmentation (Davies et al, 1999). This resultant spreading effect produces the extended distal runout observed in rock-avalanche deposits, and also reduces the runout of debris in the proximal region of the deposit.

Final remark

In this wide field of alternative theories about the hypermobility of rock avalanches, is often possible to observe the strong attachment of some proposer on his/her theory, they stick to it with no or little consideration on other theories. This kind of “stiffness” of scholars is not useful to the grow of scientific knowledge. “Certainty” should not be present in scientific research as it can never be “ultimately” reached!

In particular the problem of the long runout of rock avalanches in which so many different processes are involved, giving rise to a phenomenon of high complexity, requires an open mind to consider alternative ideas, the possible interactions among the various interconnected processes that can be involved in every single event with different weight and importance as propulsion agents for long runout rock avalanche.

The nature is never simple and always pushes everybody to go on with study and research on the “realm” of its mysteries.

REFERENCES

Bagnold, R. A. (1954); Experiments on a gravity-free dispersion of large solid spheres in a Newtonian fluid under shear. Proceedings of Royal Society of London, Ser.A 225:49-63.

Bagnold, R. A. (1956); The flow of cohesionless grains in fluids. Proceedings of Royal Society of London, Ser A, 249: 235-297.

Bieniawski Z.T. (1968); The effect of specimen size on compressive strength of coal. International Journal of Rock Mechanics and Mining Sciences, 5(4): 325–335.

Campbell, C.S., Cleary, P.W., Hopkins, M. (1995); Large-scale landslide simulations: Global deformation, velocities and basal friction. Journal of Geophysical Research, vol. 100, n. B5, 8267-8283.

Cruden, D.M. and Hungr, O. (1986); The debris of the Frank Slide and theories of rockslide-avalanche mobility. Canadian Journal of Earth Sciences, vel. 23, 425-432.

Davies, T.R.H. (1982); Spreading of rock avalanches debris by mechanical fluidization. Rock Mechanics 15, 9-24.

Davies T.R., McSaveney M.J. (2006); Rapid rock mass flow with dynamic fragmentation: inferences from the morphology and internal structure of rockslides and rock avalanches. In: Evans, S.G.; Scarascia Mugnozza, G.; Strom, A.; Hermanns, R.L. (Eds.) Landslides from Massive Rock Slope Failure; Proceedings of the NATO Advanced Research Workshop on Massive Rock Slope Failure: New Models for Hazard Assessment, Celano, Italy, 16-21 June 2002. 285-304.

Davies T.R., McSaveney M.J. (1999); Runout of dry granular avalanches. Canadian Geotechnical Journal, vol. 36, no. 2, April 1999, 313-320.

Davies, T.R.H. and McSaveney, M.J. (2009); The role of dynamic rock fragmentation in the motion of large landslides. Engineering Geology 109(1): 67-79.

Davies, T.R.H. and McSaveney, M.J. (2002); Dynamic simulation of the motion of fragmenting rock avalanches. Canadian Geotechnical Journal, vol. 39, 789-798.

Davies, T.R., McSaveney, M.J. and Beetham, R. (2006), Rapid block glides –

slide-surface fragmentation in New Zealand's Waikaremoana landslide. Quarterly Journal of Engineering Geology and Hydrogeology vol. 39, 115–129.

Davies, T.R, McSaveney, M.J., Deganutti, A.M. (2007); Dynamic fragmentation causes low rock-on-rock friction. Proc. of 1st Canada-U.S. Rock Mechanics Symposium, Vancouver, Canada, 27-31 May 2007.

Davies, T.R., McSaveney, M.J. and Hodgson, K.A. (1999). A fragmentation-spreading model for long-runout rock avalanches. Canadian Geotechnical Journal, 36: 6, 1096–1110. 1999.

Erismann T.H. (1979); Mechanisms of large landslides. Rock mechanics 12, 309-334.

Erismann T.H. (1986); Flowing, rolling, bouncing, sliding: synopsis of basic mechanisms. Acta Mechanica 64, 101-110.

Evans, S.G. (1995); The field behaviour of rock avalanches in the Canadian Cordillera. International Symposium on prediction of landslide motion, Disaster Prevention Institute, Kyoto University.

Genevois, R. (2007); Pers. comm..

Grady, D.E. and Kipp, M.E. (1987); Dynamic rock fragmentation. In Fracture Mechanics of Rock, Academic Press, London, UK, 429–475. 1987.

Guest, J.E. (1971); Geology of the far side Crater Tsiolkovsky. In: Geology and Physics of the Moon (Fielder, G. ed.) 93-103, Elsevier.

Habib, P. (1975); Production of gaseous pore pressure during rock slides. Rock Mechanics 7, 193-197.

Heim, A. (1882); Der Bergsturz von Elm. Z. Dtsch. Geol. Ges., 34, 74-115.

Heim, A. (1932); Der Bergsturz und Menschenleben. Zürich, Fretz und Wasmuth Verlag, 218 p.

Hayashi, J.N. and Self, F. (1992); A comparison of pyroclastic flow and debris avalanche mobility. Journal of Geophysical Research, 97, B6, 9063-9071.

Howard, K. (1973); Avalanche mode of motion: implications from lunar examples. Science 180, 1052-1055.

Hsü, K.J. (1975); Catastrophic debris streams (sturzstroms) generated by rockfalls. Bull. Geol. Soc. Of America, Vol. 86, 129-140.

Hsü, K.J. (1978); Albert Heim: Observations on landslides and relevance to modern interpretations. In: *Rockslides and Avalanches*, (Voight, B. ed.) vol. 1 *Natural Phenomena*, 71-93. Amsterdam, Elsevier.

Hungr, O. (1981); Dynamics of rock avalanches and other types of slope movements. PhD thesis, Univ. of Alberta, Edmonton, 500 pp.

Hungr, O. (1995); A model for the runout analysis of rapid flow slides, debris flows, and avalanches. *Canadian Geotech J.*, 32:610–623.

Hungr, O. (1990); Mobility of rock avalanches. Report of National Research Institute for Earth Science and Disaster Prevention, Japan. 46, 11-19.

Hungr, O. and Morgenstern, N.R. (1984); Experiments on the flow behaviour of granular material at high velocity in an open channel. *Geotechnique*, vol. 34, 405-413.

Johnson, B. (1978); Blackhawk landslide, California, USA (1978); In: *Rockslides and Avalanches*, (Voight, B. ed.) vol. 1 *Natural Phenomena*, 481-504. Amsterdam, Elsevier.

Kent, P.E. (1966); The transport mechanism in catastrophic rock falls. *Journal of Geology*, vol. 74, 79-83.

Kilburn, C.R.J. (2001); The flow of giant rock landslides. In: *Paradoxes in Geology*. Ken Hsü Special Volume, Chapter 13 (Eds. Briegel U and Xiao W-J.), Elsevier, 245-265.

Körner, H.J. (1977); Flow mechanism and resistances in the debris streams of large rock slides. *Bull. Int. Ass. Of Engineering Geology*, vol. 16, 101-104.

Legros F. (2001); The mobility of long runout landslides. *Engineering Geology*, 63, 301-331.

Li, T. (1983); A mathematical model for predicting the extent of a major rockfall. *Zeitschrift fur Geomorphologie*, Vol. 24, 473-482.

Liu, C.-H., Nagel, S.R., Schecter, D.A., Coppersmith, S.N., Majumdar, S., Narayan, O., and Witten, T.A. (1995); Force fluctuations in bead packs. *Science*, 269, 513-515.

McEwen, A.S. (1989); Mobility of large rock avalanches: evidence from Valles Marineris, Mars. *Geology*, vol. 17, 1111-1114.

McSaveney, M.J. (1975); The Sherman Glacier rock avalanche of 1964: Its emplacement and subsequent effects on the glacier beneath it. Columbus, Ohio, Ohio State University, Ph.D. dissertation, 426 p.

Melosh, H.J. (1997); Asteroids: Shattered but Not Dispersed. *Icarus*; vol. 129, 2, 562-564.

Nedderman, R. (1992); Statics and kinematics of granular materials. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge.

Nicoletti P.G., Sorriso-Valvo, M. (1991); Geomorphic controls of the shape and mobility of rock avalanches. *GSA Bulletin*; October 1991; v. 103; no. 10; p. 1365-1373.

Pautre, A., Sabarly, F., Schneider, B. (1974); L'effet d'échelle dans les écroulements de falaise. *C.R. 3ème Congrès ISRM, Denver*, vol. II-B, p. 859.

Pollet, N. (2004); Mouvements gravitaires rapides de grandes masses rocheuses: apports des observations de terrain à la compréhension des processus de propagation et dépôt. PhD Thesis, École Nationale des Ponts et Chaussées, Paris.

Pollet, N., Schneider J.-L.M. (2004); Dynamic disintegration processes accompanying transport of the Holocene Flims Sturzstrom (Swiss Alps). *Earth and Planetary Science Letters*, 221, (2004), 433-448.

Pollet, N., Cojean, R., Couture, R., Schneider J.-L.M., Strom, A.L., Voirin, C., Wassmer, P. (2005); A slab-on-slab model for the Flims rockslide (Swiss Alps). *Canadian Geotechnical Journal*, 42(2) 587-600.

Sammis, C. and Stacey, S.J. (1994); The micromechanics of friction in a granular layer. *PAGEOPH (Pure and Applied Geophysics)*, 142, 3/4., 777-794.

Sammis, C., King, G., and Biegel, R. (1987); The kinematics of gouge formation. *PAGEOPH (Pure and Applied Geophysics)*, 125: 777-812.

Scheidegger, A.E. (1973); On the prediction of the reach and velocity of catastrophic landslides. *Rock Mech.* 5, 231-236.

Schneider, J.-L., Wassmer, P., Ledésert, B. (1999); The fabric of the sturzstrom of Flims (Swiss Alps): Characteristics and implications on the transport mechanisms. *Comptes Rendus de l'Académie des Sciences Series IIA Earth and Planetary Science*; vol 328, 9, 607-613.

Schneider, J.-L., Fisher, R.V. (1998); Transport and emplacement mechanisms of large volcanic debris avalanches: evidence from the northwest sector of Cantal Volcano (France). *Journal of Volcanology and Geothermal Research*, vol. 83, 141–165.

Shreve, R.L., (1959); *Geology and mechanics of the Blackhawk landslide, Lucerne Valley, California*. PhD Thesis, Caltech, Pasadena, California, USA.

Shreve, R.L., (1968a); The Blackhawk landslide. *Geol. Soc. Am. Spec. Pap.* 108 47 pp.

Shreve, R.L., (1968b); Leakage and fluidization in air-layer lubricated avalanches. *Geol. Soc. Am. Bull.*, 79: 653-658.

Voight, B. (1978); Lower Gros Ventre slide, Wyoming, U.S.A. In: *Rockslides and Avalanches*, (Voight, B. ed.) vol. 1 Natural Phenomena, 113-166. Amsterdam, Elsevier.

Voight B., Janda, R.J., Glicken, H. and Douglass P.M. (1985); Nature and mechanics of the Mount St Helens rockslide-avalanche of 18 May 1980. *Geotechnique* vol. 33, no3, pp. 243-273.

Watson, R.A., Wright, H.E. (1967); The Saidmarreh landslide, Iran. *Geological Society of America*, special paper n. 123, 115-139